

amyl alcohols, diethyl malonate and methyl acetate, there should not be H-bonding possibility, and so the reversal of double layer would not take place. Therefore, there is observed a gradual decrease of interfacial tension with increasing soap concentration over the entire range.

The work on interfacial tension variations at the interface between organic liquids, referred to, and mixed aqueous salt solutions viz., KCl-HgCl_2 , $\text{KNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ etc. indicating complex formations between these salts, provides confirmation for this type of explanation. These results will be discussed in later papers.

In the case of *iso*amyl acetate (Fig. 2) such a behaviour is also observed with a very dilute solution of sodium acetate and sodium chloride, as in the case of colloidal electrolyte, sodium oleate. In a very dilute aqueous solution, the soap behaves like an ordinary electrolyte and is considerably ionised into an alkali metal cation and a fatty acid ion. At an appreciable concentration, however, the anions aggregate together to form ionic micelles (McBain).

With the saponin solution (Table II), however, only the decrease in the interfacial tension is observed with its increasing concentration over the entire range, as it would not provide ionic atmosphere like an electrolyte.

The peak in interfacial tension is maximum with *n*-butyl acetate, ethyl *isovalerate* and *sec*.-octyl alcohol, viz., 5.5, 4.69 and 6.83 dynes/cm. respectively and minimum with hexyl alcohol, ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl acetate, viz., 0.87, 0.33 and 0.74 dynes/cm. respectively. It may be possible that the peak might be related to the degree of stability of the ring character through H-bond in these cases. Further work along these lines is in progress.

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INTERFACIAL TENSION OF LIQUIDS HAVING H-BOND RING STRUCTURE AND COMPLEX FORMATION. PART I. $\text{HgCl}_2\text{-KCl-H}_2\text{O}$ SYSTEM

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Measurements of interfacial tension between *n*-butyl acetate and solutions containing KCl and HgCl_2 in varying proportions indicate the formation of seven complexes in solution between KCl and HgCl_2 , viz. (1) $4\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (2) $3\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (3) $2\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (4) $3\text{KCl} \cdot 2\text{HgCl}_2$, (5) $\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (6) $2\text{KCl} \cdot 3\text{HgCl}_2$ and (7) $\text{KCl} \cdot 2\text{HgCl}_2$.

The formation of three complexes between HgCl_2 and KCl in solution, namely, $\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, $2\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, and $3\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ has been shown by measurements of solubility, conductivity and surface tension (Tichomiroff, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 39, 731; Foote, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 38, 236; Arcay and Marcot, *Compt. rend.*,

1939, 209, 881). The existence of complex $K_4(HgCl_6)$ in solution has been reported by others (Benrath, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 86, 258; Dey, *Curr. Sci.*, 1946, 15, 24). Tournoux's investigations (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1919, ix, 11, 225) indicate the formation of complexes: (1) $HgCl_2 \cdot 2KCl \cdot H_2O$ (2) $HgCl_2 \cdot KCl \cdot 3/4 H_2O$, (3) $3HgCl_2 \cdot 2KCl \cdot 5/3 H_2O$, (4) $2HgCl_2 \cdot 3KCl \cdot 3/5 H_2O$ and (5) $2HgCl_2 \cdot KCl \cdot H_2O$. The existence of $(HgCl_3)^-$ and $(HgCl_4)^{--}$ ions has been shown in solution by the study of solubility and Raman spectra (Garret, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2744; Nayar and Saraf, this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 312). The viscosity, refractive index and surface tension data (Nayar *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, 29, 241-254) obtained by the method of monovariation reveal the formation of six complexes: (1) $4KCl \cdot HgCl_2$, (2) $2KCl \cdot HgCl_2$, (3) $3KCl \cdot 2HgCl_2$, (4) $KCl \cdot HgCl_2$, (5) $2KCl \cdot 3HgCl_2$ and (6) $KCl \cdot 2HgCl_2$.

In the present investigation the method of monovariation (Nayar, *loc. cit.*), which is eminently suited for the study of complexes in solution, has been adopted for interfacial tension measurements by the drop number method (Kazi and Desai this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 209) using *n*-butyl acetate against a series of mixed solutions of $HgCl_2$ and KCl .

EXPERIMENTAL

The substances used were of A. R. quality (B. D. H.). The ester was further purified by treatment with sodium carbonate solution, washing with water, drying and distilling. The middle fraction was utilised for the purpose. Potassium and mercuric chlorides were further purified by repeated crystallisations from pure distilled water. $HgCl_2$ or KCl (24 c.c.) solutions were run into a glass-stoppered 100 c.c. flask from a calibrated burette. The requisite volumes of either KCl or $HgCl_2$ were then added and the mixture made up to 100 c.c. with distilled water. The results obtained by measurements of the interfacial tension of the solutions at 30° are shown graphically in Fig 1 which also gives the results with the system $HgCl_2$ - $NaCl$ - H_2O .

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows peaks corresponding to the formation of complex compounds of molecular formulae: $4KCl \cdot HgCl_2$, $3KCl \cdot HgCl_2$, $2KCl \cdot HgCl_2$, $3KCl \cdot 2HgCl_2$, $KCl \cdot HgCl_2$, $2KCl \cdot 3HgCl_2$ and $KCl \cdot 2HgCl_2$. The tendency for complex formation is not evident in $HgCl_2$ - $NaCl$ - H_2O system.

The authors are inclined to take the view that the formation of these complexes corresponds to

sequence resulting from changes in interionic character, due to variations in electrolyte concentration. The complex $3KCl \cdot HgCl_2$ is interpreted in the ratio $6KCl \cdot 2HgCl_2$

for the sequence. The complex $2\text{KCl} \cdot 3\text{HgCl}_2$ is expressed as $\left\{ \begin{matrix} \text{K}_2 (\text{HgCl}_4) \\ 2 \text{HgCl}_2 \end{matrix} \right.$ and not as $\left\{ \begin{matrix} 2 \text{K} (\text{HgCl}_4) \\ \text{HgCl}_2 \end{matrix} \right.$, because in that case the interionic character would not suffer such a significant change from that of (7) as to warrant maximum tension, corresponding to the peak in the curves.

FIG. 1

M/25-KCl(c.c.) added to 24 c.c. of M/50-HgCl₂.

The method is likely to prove a very sensitive one, because it reveals the tendency of complex formation in solutions of even very low concentrations. It therefore offers an advantage in the case of sparingly soluble salts or when salts are sparingly available.

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